

Effect of simple and complex fertilizers on rice yield, Peshawar, Pakistan.^a

Treatment NPK (kg/ha)	Fertilizer	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw ^b yield (t/ha)	Value cost ratio ^c	panicles ^b /m ²
		1982	1983	Mean			
0-0-0	No fertilizer	4.8 d	5.8 b	5.3 b	6.3 b	—	270 c
120-0-0	Urea	7.2 c	7.3 a	7.3 a	14.0 a	4.37	346 bc
120-40-0	Urea+ SSP	7.6 b	8.2 a	7.9 a	14.1 a	4.04	395 ab
120-40-0	Urea+ DAP	7.9 a	8.0 a	8.0 a	14.9 a	4.06	424 a
120-40-0	Urea + NP	7.1 c	7.3 a	7.2 a	12.3 a	2.58	387 ab

^aMeans followed by similar letters do not differ significantly at 5% level. ^b1983 data on a fresh weight basis. ^cValue of rice = \$10/100 kg. Cost of fertilizers: urea, \$19.00/100 kg; SSP, \$14.14/100 kg; DAP, \$17.28/100 kg; NP, \$13.85/100 kg. Value of straw is not included.

duced the highest straw yield and panicles /m². Urea plus DAP yielded the highest net return – a value cost ratio of 4.06.

DAP is a better complex fertilizer for rice than the others tested. Response to NP was poor because it contains 9% nitrate N, which is susceptible to leaching and denitrification. □

Nitrogen fertilization for short-duration rices

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Short-duration (105-110 d) rice varieties are grown Jun-Sep in the Cauvery Delta. We evaluated the response of ADT31 (1981) and ADT36 (1982) to 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha. Soil at TNRRI is a clay loam with low available N and pH 7.5. Urea was applied 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. P and K at 50 kg/ha were applied basally. Plant height and number of panicles/hill

Effect of different N levels on plant height and panicles/hill at flowering and grain yield of short-duration varieties, Aduthurai, India.

N (kg/ha)	ADT31			ADT36		
	Height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	75	4.0	3.4	68	4.9	3.5
30	82	4.6	4.5	74	5.4	4.1
60	87	5.3	4.7	76	5.9	4.8
90	91	5.6	5.2	78	6.2	5.1
120	93	5.9	6.1	81	6.5	5.5
CD (P0.05)	2	0.5	0.6	3	0.4	0.3

were recorded at flowering and the grain yield at 14% moisture.

Both varieties grew taller with increased N. Maximum height was at 120 kg N/ha. Number of panicles/hill did

not increase significantly between 90 and 120 kg N/ha. ADT31 yields at 90 and 120 kg N/ha were similar and ADT36 yielded significantly higher at 120 kg N/ha (see table). □

Preventing zinc deficiency in wetland rice

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Zn fertilizer application is becoming important as more land with Zn deficiency is discovered. Cheap, efficient Zn sources must be identified and application methodology improved. We studied the

Table 1. Soil characteristics in Zn application trials in Ludhiana, India.

Soil characteristic	Pot experiment	Field experiment
pH	8.6	8.8
Organic C (%)	0.39	0.37
Ec (mmho/cm)	0.20	0.13
Texture	Sandy loam	Sandy clay loam
Zn (ppm)	0.36	0.35

Table 2. Methods of Zn application and Zn content of wetland rice, Ludhiana, India.

Method	Zn content (ppm) at different plant ages				Grain maturity
	16 d	32 d	48 d	64 d	
No Zn	20	22	24	18	18
Root dip	85	46	38	34	29
Nursery application	112	35	31	28	28
Crop application	37	33	28	28	28
CD at 5%	5.6	6.5	3.9	4.7	2.7

Methods of Zn application and rice yield, Ludhiana, India.